

EFFECTIVE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A WELDLINE IN A SHORT GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 66 BASED ON X-RAY MICRO-TOMOGRAPHY AND FINITE ELEMENT COMPUTATION

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ABSTRACT

An ever occurring injection moulding artefact in short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics (SGFRTs) is weldline formation commonly considered as zone of mechanical weakness. Based on recent computer simulation packages, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) are able to precisely predict weldline location and extent even within complex-shaped parts [1,2]. However, no one can provide a full quantitative description of the corresponding local mechanical properties so far. Mechanical characterisation procedures are limitless at the macro-scale because of the restricted width of weldline affected-zones [3,4]. In order to quantify the local anisotropic elastic properties within a weldline, we combine X-Ray micro-tomography with a two-scale finite element computation. An open-hole plate obtained by injection moulding of 35 wt% short glass fibre reinforced polyamide 66 is considered. The chosen geometry has the advantage to generate a weldline region due to a central open hole and to generate non symmetric fibre orientation. X-Ray micro-tomography shows a marked V-shape fibre distribution in the core zone of the weldline. Qualitative and quantitative analyses of fibre orientation reveal the existence of high level of out-of-plane orientations in the closest zone to the open-hole. Furthermore, deformation monitoring by Digital Image Correlation technique (DIC) indicates that, during monotonic tensile tests, the effect of the out-of-plane orientations cannot be neglected locally in the weldline area near the open-hole. Analysis of numerical results related to the averaged micro-mechanical/ macro-mechanical models shows small difference between Young's moduli components. But, predictions related to the macroscopic mechanical model demonstrate that Poisson's ratio components are difficult to achieve because of the reduced number of elements in comparison to the microscopic model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastics reinforced with heterogeneously dispersed short glass fibres are gaining wider and more general usage for semi-structural automotive applications. These materials commonly shaped by injection moulding process are developed by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) thanks to their mechanical performance and relatively low processing cost. It is commonly acknowledged that mechanical properties of Short Glass Fibre Reinforced Thermoplastics (SGFRTs) depend on the structural arrangement of fibres. Thus, a more particular attention should be accorded to unusual shapes, which encompass ribs, stress concentration forms and/or abrupt thickness variations. These are the birth sites of some inevitable process-related aberrations. An ever occurring flaw is the formation of weldlines, when multiple streams of a molten thermoplastic matrix come into contact while filling a

mould's cavity [5]. Weldlines have always been considered as elements of uncertainty due to their low mechanical properties. In the case of SGFRTs, weldlines have poor reinforcement across the welding joint since the fibres tend preferentially to align along the main mould flow direction. Consequently, the reinforcing effect of fibres is degenerated resulting in weakness zones with low mechanical properties comparable to those of the bulk matrix [6–8,3,9].

In the particular case of automotive components, polyamide composites are mainly used for under-the-hood applications. In such environment, these materials are continuously exposed to the effect of combined loads: thermal, mechanical and moisture absorption/drying cycles resulting in prompt fatigue and aging. In order to guarantee high-performance components, an appropriate fatigue design approach should be adopted to accurately estimate the part lifetime especially in critical zones [10–14]. Within this line of thought, OEMs rely more and more on computer simulation packages to optimise the design of complex shapes. The dedicated software can simulate the mould's cavity filling, locate the eventual weldline-infested-areas and estimate their extent. However, none of the actual packages can accurately assess local weldline mechanical properties since there is still no adequate mathematical model so far [1,2]. To overcome numerical methods limitations, experimental characterisation studies on weldlines have long been performed, of which the majority is limited to the macro scale [6,7,15,16]. At the macro scale, a weldline-infested-zone corresponds to a sharp interface limiting accessibility to local mechanical properties.

Recent advances in microstructure characterisation techniques have extended the analyses of structural arrangements within SGFRTs to higher levels of precision. X-ray micro-tomography technique has proved its capacity to provide detailed microstructural data based on X-Ray absorption differences between the material constituents. Furthermore, resolutions down to few microns can be easily reached with appropriate laboratory equipments [17–20]. In this study, we combine X-ray micro-tomography with a two-scale finite element model to probe the real microstructural arrangement of short glass fibres within a weldline and to compute corresponding effective properties assuming local orthotropy. For this purpose, we firstly investigate fibre orientation distribution. Secondly, we use digital image correlation technique to monitor displacement fields in the vicinity of the weldline zone during monotonic tensile tests and to investigate the effect of out-of-plane fibre orientations on the resulting mechanical behaviour. Finally, we combine micro-tomography data with finite element computations to assess the orthotropic mechanical properties. Due to the large number of degrees of freedom prohibiting a full resolution image based finite element computation; we adopt a two-scale numerical homogenisation method.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

The material used in this study is a polyamide 6.6 reinforced with 35 wt% of short E-glass fibres. The studied grade is commercialised by DuPontTM under the trade name Zytel®70G35 HSLX. The fibres have an average length of 250 μm and a nominal diameter of 10 μm . The selected grade is generally used in automotive parts working in the vicinity of the car engine such as intake manifolds, inlet gas compressor exit and fuel injection rails [10,21]. In this study, we use a mild notched plate obtained by injection moulding process as illustrated in Figure 1a. The adopted configuration has the advantage to induce a strongly anisotropic fibre orientation distribution [22]. Moreover, it causes the formation of a hot weldline due to a circular opening located at the centre. Furthermore, the lateral restrained injection gate guarantees a non-symmetric fibre arrangement along the main length of the specimen.

2.2. X-RAY TOMOGRAPHY SCANS

Microstructural analyses are performed with an X-Ray micro-tomography system generating a conical beam. Radiographies are acquired via a CCD camera with a detection frame of 4000×2624 pixels. Detection parameters are adjusted to reach a voxel size of 2.53 μm during all scans, which

almost corresponds to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the mean glass fibre diameter. A total of 1664 phase contrast images are collected by imposing small angular increments to cover 360° . Collected individual cross-sections of the sample are then reconstructed by applying the filtered back-projection method using X-Act software from Rx-Solutions. Complementary details about acquisition parameters are listed in Table 1.

<i>Voltage</i> [kV]	<i>Current intensity</i> [μ A]	<i>Beam energy</i> [W]	<i>Projections</i>	<i>Scan time</i> [min]	<i>Voxel-size</i> [μ m]	<i>Target</i>	<i>Average</i>
60	60	3,48	1664	67	2,53	Mo	8

Table 1. X-Ray micro-tomography acquisition parameters.

Two samples of $3 \times 10 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ are extracted along the same weldline. As illustrated in Figure 1a, the sample S_1 is located at the edge of the open-hole while the sample S_2 is shifted laterally by a 30mm distance from the first sample. The distance between the samples has not been optimised. However, it is imposed to investigate the microstructural changes at two different regions along the welding joint.

Figure 1. a) Geometry of the studied open-hole plate (dimensions in [mm]). The locations of the scanned samples are shaded in grey color. b) Schematic revealing sample positions in the injection moulded plate for monotonic tests.

2.3.MECHANICAL TESTS

Monotonic tensile tests are conducted on an Instron 1185 mechanical testing machine equipped with a 5kN load cell. Tests are performed at room temperature (23°C) at a fixed crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. During the mechanical tests, displacements at the surface of the samples are monitored by DIC using the VIC-2DTM system.

3. DATA ANALYSIS & EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1.MICROSTRUCTURE ACCOMMODATION PROTOCOL

The adopted protocol is based on consecutive processes implemented using the open domain software ImageJ. Three-dimensional reconstructed microstructures are post-processed to cope with the large number of planned micro-scale finite element computations. Initially, the brightness of the stacked raw is calibrated to visually discriminate between fibres and matrix. Adjusted images are then conditionally converted from 32bits to 8bits with respect of grey level distribution similarities to avoid excessive information loss. Due to computational resource limitations, the voxel resolution is shifted down by rescaling all images by a factor of 2. The physical extent of the composite is delimited by defining the largest field of view exclusively bounding the microstructure. The global 3D volumes are cropped resulting in 50 voxels side sub-domains. The obtained sub-domains serve as inputs to the micro-scale finite element model. For such purpose, the grey scale acquired images are segmented by applying an automatic threshold to each image. This operation is controlled by measuring the resulting fibre volume fractions.

3.2. FIBRE ORIENTATION

Qualitative analysis of micro-tomography data reveals wide differences in fibre orientation as illustrated in Figure 2. Fibre distribution in the sample S_1 reveals a characteristic in plane V-shape fibre distribution with existence of out-of-plane fibres in the core and especially near the open-hole. This region is the place where melt fronts weld. It expands throughout the sample thickness with a typical thickness of $2250 \mu\text{m}$. On the other hand, the sample S_2 presents a narrower weld region at the core region of the sample. The corresponding thickness of the weld region is less important compared to S_1 ($<440 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 2. X-Ray micro-tomography images illustrating fibre orientation evolution through the thickness. The images on the top correspond to S_1 where those on the bottom correspond to S_2 .

A second protocol is applied to extract fibre orientation distributions. Fibrous network is submitted to a first 2D skeletonisation operation followed by 3D labelling step. The major axis of the skeleton of each individual fibre or cluster is identified in its bounding box. This axis is selected based on the lowest sum of all shortest distances between the candidate axis and those voxels belonging to the skeleton. The 3D orientation of the optimal axis is described by the azimuthal (θ) and elevation (φ) angles. The first one defines the orientation in the XY plane where the second one is related to the inclination with respect to Z axis. To quantitatively compare fibre orientation between the tested samples, angular measurements obtained from the previous fibre processing protocol are used to compute the components of second order orientation tensors. For this purpose, a home-developed Matlab script is implemented according to the work of Bay and Tucker [23]. For each elementary volume, the corresponding angles are used to evaluate the mean orientation tensor components of each 2D plane along the sample depth (Z axis). All orientation components are presented as a function of the normalized thickness (where the normalized thickness corresponds to the central plane depth

reported to the global thickness of the sample). For sake of clarity, and to reduce noise effect related to local orientation distribution, each point of the plotted curves corresponds to an average of 10 consecutive planes.

As illustrated in Figure 3, a_{xx} components have the highest values across the thickness of both samples. In the case of the sample S1 respectively the sample S2, almost 70% (respectively 85%) are aligned in the mould flow direction (X axis). Furthermore, the characteristic symmetric skin-shell-core structure can only be identified in the sample S₂ far from the open-hole. On the other hand, the sample S₁; the nearest to the open-hole; has the highest fraction of fibres oriented out of the plane XY with an average of 21% fibre orientations.

Figure 3. Evolution of the principle components of second order orientation tensors relative to the delimited fields-of-view of the sample S₁ (in solid marks) and S₂ (in hollow marks).

3.3. DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

In order to investigate the effect of fibre orientations on the resulting mechanical deformation, two monotonic tensile tests are performed and displacement field at the surface of the specimens is monitored using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) acquisition system. The first tensile test is conducted on the whole specimen geometry with the open-hole. The computed deformation fields (Figures 4.a-c) illustrate asymmetric deformation field between the areas on the top and the bottom of the open-hole, which can be explained by the structural heterogeneity induced by an anisotropic fibres caused by the combined effect of the weldline and the injection gate location. This observation has been confirmed in another study where the effect of microstructure on stress distributions around the hole has been evaluated [22]. A complementary analysis is performed to evaluate the local effect of fibre orientation anisotropy within the weldline. To limit the stress concentration effect related to the circular notch, $20 \times 40 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$ samples are cut tangentially to the open-hole as illustrated by the shaded zone in the Figure 1.b. In the current study, we assume that the weldline is located along the median axis of the largest dimension of the sample. In other terms we suppose that for the 20mm zone after the open-hole, the effect related to the injection gate location can be neglected. Tensile tests are performed along the main direction of the samples. Computed Lagrange deformation fields corresponding to 49 MPa stress level (where the ultimate stress value is 62 MPa) are illustrated in Figures 4.d-f. The computed Lagrange E_{xx} deformation fields show that the weldline zone is easily detectible and it corresponds to the zone of highest deformation levels. The non-symmetry exhibited by the E_{yy} and E_{xy} fields confirms the existence of an anisotropic fibre distribution. We recall that the open-hole is located at the left of all presented deformation fields supposed to the sample surface. Moreover, E_{xx} and E_{yy} Lagrange deformation levels respectively exhibit a confined effect at the most left side of the

deformation fields. This region corresponds to the zone from where the sample S_1 is extracted. Thus, the anisotropy is most likely to be induced by the elevated fraction of out-of-plane oriented fibres. Such a result indicates that, locally in the weldline zone according to the applied load direction, out-of-plane orientations should not be neglected since they can modify the evaluation of local mechanical properties.

Figure 4. (a-c) Strain fields distribution corresponding to 65 MPa stress level. (d-f) Strain fields distribution corresponding to 49 MPa stress level.

4. NUMERICAL MODELLING

4.1. MODELLING TECHNIQUE

Finite element computation is performed based on voxel to finite element conversion scheme [24]. Due to the large resources required to perform numerical computations, the adopted strategy is decomposed into two scales. First, 3D X-Ray micro-tomography data are post-processed to increase voxel size from $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ to $5 \mu\text{m}$. A structured meshing is performed using 3D-8 node elements corresponding to the voxel size and with three displacement components U_X , U_Y and U_Z per each node. At this level, each micro-composite cubic domain of $250 \mu\text{m}$ extent is submitted to a virtual mechanical test in the three main directions of the global volume referential with imposing periodic boundary conditions. Thus, for each micro-domain, the corresponding orthotropic mechanical properties are evaluated in a post processing phase by extracting 9 engineering constants. The obtained properties are then attributed to an equivalent homogeneous domain of the same size. Second, the same virtual test procedure is performed to assess the macro-scale orthotropic mechanical parameters of the global scanned composite domain formed by assembling the equivalent homogeneous micro-composite domains. For more precision, all finite element computations are performed using a workstation with the following specifications: 12-core Xeon CPU X565, 2.67 GHz, 48GB RAM. Figure 5 provides a schematic, which summarises the adopted numerical strategy.

Figure 5. Schematic of the adopted multi-scale finite element model.

4.2. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Similar computations are performed to evaluate the effective mechanical parameters of both analysed samples. Figure 6 details the obtained results from the micro-scale and macro-scale models. The values resulting from the micromechanical model are averages performed on all cells belonging to a particular volume. Despite elastic moduli from both approaches are in good agreement, estimated Poisson's ratio show some differences. This can be explained by the large variation of lateral displacement in the macroscopic model which does not allow a proper evaluation of some components notably n_{xy} and n_{zy} .

Figure 6: Predicted Young's Moduli and Poisson's Coefficients of the studied short fibre reinforced thermoplastic based on the orthotropy assumption. The values resulting from the micromechanical model are averages performed on all sub-domains.

5. CONCLUSIONS

X-Ray micro-Tomography is an efficient imaging technique for the analysis of microstructural fibre arrangement of two different samples extracted from the same welding joint. Analysis of structural data reveals a characteristic in-plane fibre orientation distribution with presence of non-negligible fraction of out-of-plane fibres especially in the nearest region to the open-hole. Furthermore, precise measurement of weldline dimensions is achieved within the scanned zones. Complementary analysis of second order orientation tensor main components allows the quantification of out-of-plane fibre fraction. The conducted monotonic tensile tests monitored with the DIC technique demonstrate a substantial effect of out-of-plane fibres, which results in strain localisation. On the other hand, coupling of X-Ray tomography results with the adopted two-scale finite element method concludes on orthotropic mechanical behaviour of the studied composite. Elastic moduli of both micro and macro scale models are similar however Poisson's ratios are more difficult to evaluate. The difficulty can be explained by large variation of lateral displacement in the macroscopic model. Our adopted method is able to provide predictions of all engineering constants in presence of varied fibre environment induced by the presence of the weldline.

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